

Considering the steps (i)-(iii) and applying steady state conditions with respect to M^+ the rate law may be written as eqn. (4) with safe assumption that the values of k_2 is low so that $k_{-1} \gg k_2$ [Ce(IV)] holds good.

$$-\frac{d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1}} [Ce(IV)][M][H^+] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{or rate} = k_1^{\ddagger} [Ce(IV)][M][H^+] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{where } k_1^{\ddagger} = k_1 k_2 / k_{-1}$$

At constant $[H^+]$, eqn. (5) may be written as eqn. (6),

$$\text{rate} = k_2^{\ddagger} [Ce(IV)][M] \quad \dots (6)$$

At constant $[M]$, eqn. (6) may be written as eqn. (7)

$$\text{rate} = k_1 [Ce(IV)] \quad \dots (7)$$

The rate laws (5), (6) and (7) are in complete agreement with observed kinetics. Interaction between two similarly charged species in the proposed rate determining step (ii) is in complete accord with positive effect of ionic strength of the medium leading to rate law (5) as valid.

References

1. K. K. SENGUPTA and S. ADITYA, *Z. Phys. Chemie.*, 1963, **38**, 126.
2. F. R. DUKE and A. A. FORIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2790.
3. F. R. DUKE and F. R. BREMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5179.
4. S. B. HANNA, S. ALKASHIMI, W. H. WEBB and H. R. CARROLL, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1969, **246**, 231.
5. S. B. HANNA, R. K. HESSLEY, W. H. WEBB and W. R. CARROLL, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1971, **255**, 83.
6. S. B. HANNA and R. K. HESSLEY, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1971, **7**, 83.
7. S. B. HANNA, R. K. HESSLEY, W. R. CARROLL and W. H. WEBB, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 1097.
8. S. B. HANNA, W. R. CARROLL, S. A. ATTIGA and W. H. WEBB, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1975, **30b**, 409.
9. B. SINGH, C. P. S. GAUR, R. B. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 59.
10. S. VENKATKRISHNAN and M. SANTAPPA, *J. Phys. Chemia. New Folge*, 1968, **16**, 73.
11. G. HARGREAVES and L. H. SUTCLIFFE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **53**, 1105.
12. J. HARDWICK and E. ROBERTSON, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 828.
13. K. G. EVERETT and D. A. SKOOG, *Analyt. Chemia.*, 1971, **43**, 1541.
14. F. R. DUKE and F. R. PARCHEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1540.

15. R. C. SPOONER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 167.
16. L. J. HEIDT and M. E. SMITH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **70**, 2476.
17. F. B. BAKER, T. W. NEWTON and M. KHAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 109.

Reaction of β -Mercaptoethanol with α , β -Unsaturated Steroidal Ketones : Synthesis of Steroidal Thioethers

SHAFIULLAH*, SHAMSUZZAMAN and B. Z. KHAN
Steroidal Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 20 May 1983, revised 6 June 1983,
accepted 15 September 1983

IN continuation to our previous studies¹⁻⁴, we carried out the synthesis of steroidal thioethers (III-VII) by the reaction of β -mercaptoethanol with α , β -unsaturated 7-ketosteroids (I and II) in acetic acid using BF_3 -etherate as catalyst. By this method we got some new thioethers (III, VI, VII) in addition to IV and V, which were obtained (after acetylation of the products) by the previous method⁴. Thioethers had been tested for antiinflammatory, neurotropic, bactericidal, fungicidal, anticholesteremic and hypolipemic activities⁵⁻⁸. Few others were reported as tranquilizers⁹. Steroidal thioethers were also used to assay steroidal hormones using radio-immunoassay technique¹⁰. These physiological observations inspired us to undertake the present work.

Characterization of these thioethers was made on the basis of their spectral data.

3β -Acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one (I)¹¹ on treatment with β -mercaptoethanol in acetic acid, using BF_3 -etherate as catalyst afforded five thioethers.

3β -Acetoxy-4 α -acetoxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (III), m.p. 69-70°, yield 32%. IR $\nu_{\max}$:

1740, 1025 (O-C-CH₃), 1665 cm⁻¹ (C=C-C=O).
NMR : δ 5.68 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.2 (m, 3H, -OCH₂, C3 α -H), 2.86 (m, 3H, -SCH₂, C4 β -H), 2.02 (s, 6H, 2X-O-C-CH₃). (Found : C, 70.74 ; H, 9.31. C₃₃H₅₂O₅S requires C, 70.71 ; H, 9.29%).

3β -Acetoxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (IV), m.p. 88-89°, yield 23%. IR $\nu_{\max}$: 1735, 1020

1740, 1025 (O-C-CH₃), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=C-C=O). NMR : δ 5.6 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.18 (t, 2H, -OCH₂), 2.65 (m, 3H, -SCH₂, C3 α -H), 2.02 (s, 3H, O-C-CH₃). (Found : C, 74.14 ; H, 9.99. C₃₁H₅₀O₅S requires C, 74.10 ; H, 9.96%).

3 α -Acetoxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (V), m.p. 82-83°, yield 15%. IR $\nu_{\max}$: 1735, 1025

$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ \text{O}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \end{array}$, 1665 cm^{-1} (C=C-C=O). NMR: δ 5.6 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.14 (t, 2H, -OCH₂), 2.32 (m, 1H, C3 β -H; W_{1/2}=7Hz; equatorial), 2.6 (t, 2H,

$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ -\text{SCH}_2 \end{array}$, 2.01 (s, 3H, O-C-CH₃). (Found: C, 74.12; H, 9.98. C₃₁H₅₀O₃S requires C, 74.10; H, 9.96%).

4 α -Acetoxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (VI),

$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ \text{O}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \end{array}$, semisolid, yield 8%. IR $\nu_{\max}$: 1740, 1030 (O-C-CH₃), 1665 cm^{-1} (C=C-C=O). NMR: δ 5.61 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.28 (t, 2H, -OCH₂), 3.65 (t, 1H, C4 β -H; J=12 Hz; axial), 2.8 (t, -SCH₂), 2.01 (s, 3H,

$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ \text{O}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \end{array}$). (Found: C, 74.15; H, 9.99. C₃₁H₅₀O₃S requires C, 74.10; H, 9.96%).

4 α -Hydroxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (VII), semisolid, yield 5%. IR $\nu_{\max}$: 3390 (-OH), 1665 cm^{-1} (C=C-C=O). NMR: δ 5.62 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.22 (t, 2H, -OCH₂), 3.68 (t, 1H, C4 β -H; J=12 Hz; axial), 2.88 (t, 2H, -SCH₂). (Found: C, 75.68; H, 10.47. C₂₉H₄₈O₂S requires C, 75.65; H, 10.43%).

3 β -Chlorocholest-5-en-7-one (II)¹² on similar treatment with β -mercaptoethanol afforded compounds IV (38%), V (28%), VI (7%) and VII (4%).

Acetylation of VII with pyridine acetic anhydride provided a semisolid compound which was found identical with VI in all respects.

Acknowledgement

The financial support from the C.S.I.R., New Delhi as Senior Research Fellowship (S.Z. and B.Z.K.) is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. SHAFIULLAH, H. ALI, H. OGURA and H. TAKAYANAGI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1981, **54**, 3006.
2. SHAFIULLAH, M. A. GHAFFARI and S. HUSAIN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1982, **324**, 155.
3. SHAFIULLAH, M. A. GHAFFARI, H. ALI, S. ZAMAN, H. OGURA and H. TAKAYANAGI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20B**, 441.
4. SHAFIULLAH, SHAMSUZZAMAN, H. ALI and M. A. GHAFFARI, *Synthetic Commun.*, 1981, **11**, 751.
5. N. V. BOGOSLOVSKII, N. M. KOJBINA, L. M. OBVINTSEVA and E. L. PIDEMSKII, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1979, **13**, 53.
6. H. A. BRANDMAN, J. E. FREUDEWALD, M. MANOWITZ, E. J. NIKAWITZ and F. H. SHARPELL, JR., *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, **92**, 41776a.
7. Z. LUDWIG, F. JOHANNA and T. KURT, *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **88**, 89673j.
8. L. VICTOR and L. LOUIS, *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **88**, 50510d.
9. A. F. HIRSCH, *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **89**, 108112q.
10. J. ELIASSAF, *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **87**, 152472q.
11. W. G. DAUBEN and G. J. FONKEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4736.
12. A. H. MILBURN and E. V. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1736.